

Designing Batik and Artificial Batik Differentiator Applications Using Tensorflow

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Abstract: Batik is the pride and masterpiece heritage of Indonesia. Batik has awarded as cultural heritage from UNESCO on October 2nd, 2009 and it is significantly affected to batik industry afterward. UNESCO has recognized batik as a traditional textile produced by using a technique of wax-resist dyeing applied to the fabric. Many products are produced to resemble batik, however along with technological innovations the products do not use hot wax. It will be difficult for the public to distinguish between the real batik and artificial batik available on the market. In order to determine whether the item is a real batik product or a falsified product, a tool is required. Center for Crafts and Batik has conducted research on making the "Batik Analyzer" software. The software's design is made using "deep learning" technology. The software uses TensorFlow. TensorFlow is a computational framework for making "machine learning" models. Machines are trained to be able to learn the difference in products by providing learning tools in the form of authentic batik which are: stamp batik and hand-written batik; artificial product which are: batik print imitation, cold wax batik print imitation, and burn-out print batik imitation products. The application that was created later was designed to run on an Android-based smartphone or tablet. Applications are then trained to recognize the product. The used data set is taken at The Center for Crafts and Batik for each type of fabrics to be distinguished. The results of the exercise are tested to be able to recognize the product. From the results of the training, it can be found that the software can distinguish products with 70 percent accuracy.

Keywords: batik; batik analyzer; stamped batik; hand written batik; artificial batik; TensorFlow
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1. Introduction

The process of making batik goes through several stages. These steps are done manually. In written batik, starting with the making pattern on the fabric using a pencil. For one piece of written batik, complex pattern work can take days. Pattern work is continued with the wax sticking work on the edge of the motif or transferring motifs which in batik terms are called klowong. Sticking the wax to the klowong section is the longest job. The motif was first completed with the first coloring work. If you want there are several colors in a piece of fabric, then the first color you want is received by the process of closing the parts with melted

wax (called : *nembok*). The *nembok* work continued to the coloring. To eliminate the wax, the wax release process is done by boiling it. The wax that sticks to the fabric will come loose and float on the surface of the water. The work of making batik can take a month or more. Batik stamps are made faster than batik. By using tools called *canting cap*, *nglowong* work can be accelerated to just a few hours.

Along with the development and demands of the economy, many artificial batik has been produced. Its manufacture does not involve the process of sticking hot wax for color resist. Artificial batik can be made faster and can be done in mass scale. Stated that the popularity of batik affected the use of textile technology which was able to accelerate the production of batik-patterned fabrics. This technology is capable to produce tens to hundreds of pieces of batik cloth in a day. However, the acceleration of production capability eliminated the cultural essence of the batik, because batik which is recognized as a cultural heritage is batik that uses hot wax (batik wax) with the main equipment called *canting tulis*, batik stamp, or a combination of both [1]. The artificial batik is intended to include color printing, color removal printing, cold wax printing or a combination of several of these techniques. The use of these techniques is mostly to make products resembling batik motif. The artificial product is indeed similar to batik. Artificial batik products on the market are easier to find. This is because the price is relatively cheaper. Historically printing batik can be categorized as a counterfeit product because it is not in accordance with the actual definition and technique of batik and only attempts to resemble it [2]. Batik printing was indeed introduced with the aim of rivaling the authentic batik. By resembling original batik, for ordinary people will be fooled and increase the desire to buy these products. To determine whether the item is a real batik product or a falsified product, a tool is required for this purpose. Center for Crafts and Batik has conduct research on making the "Batik Analyzer" software. Design software made using "deep learning" technology .

Machine learning is a subfield of computer science that has the ability to learn new codes and instructions without being explicitly programmed to do. Machine learning is closely related to the computational field of statistics that focuses on making predictions or forecasting using computers [4]. Machine learning learn with the data entered and can be applied in many applications. Lawrence revealed that machine learning has been successfully applied to many things, including speech recognition, visual object recognition, motorcycle taxi detection and application to other domains such as drug discovery and genomics [4]. Li and his friends applied TensorFlow to analyze data on diabetics [5]. One of the frameworks for using machine learning is TensorFlow .

Tensorflow is a framework for building machine learning. Tensorflow was developed by engineers and researchers working at google companies. The Tensorflow software library uses a data flow graph that describes mathematical calculations with nodes and edges. Each node in a graph represents a mathematical operation, while an edge represents a relationship between nodes [3]. Flow sensors have several advantages, including the Tensorflow system is very flexible and provides many models, the Tensorflow architecture is very modular so that it can be used per part or used simultaneously, applications built using Tensorflow are very

portable for use in notebooks, desktops and even mobile computing platforms. Another advantage is that Tensorflow allows programmers to maximize existing hardware [4].

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Materials

The tools needed in this study are computers that have adequate processor and graphic specifications, digital cameras, android phones, camera lights, and digital microscopes. The sample fabrics included authentic batik and artificial batik. The number of samples is 1030 samples, consisting of 254 hand-written batik, 271 stamp batik , 299 batik print imitation, 119 burn-out print batik imitation, and 88 cold wax batik print imitation. Each sample is given an identity that matches the type of manufacturing process. Another material used is deep learning software, namely Tensorflow .

2.2. Installing Tensorflow on a computer

High-performance computers are installed TensorFlow, an open source API developed by Google for Machine learning and Deep Learning, but can also be used for others, such as numerical calculations. This framework can be used both as a backend, with C ++, and frontend in Python. This process involves the github fork from TensorFlow object detection. Python is equipped with a labelling module.

2.3. Collecting and Labelling datasets

Each sample (included authentic batik and artificial batik) collected is then checked by the batik evaluator to determine the type of batik or type of artificial batik based on the manufacturing process. Each sample is given an identification. The sample that has been identified is then photographed in several different places. Image capture is uniformed with a magnification of 60 times, 20 times and a full frame image. Obtained sample images are 5140 images. The results of taking pictures using a digital microscope and smartphone cameras are placed in folders according to the clothes type. Each picture is labeled respectively. The finished label file has an xml extension. Files in the form of xml are then converted into CSV files so that they can be collected in 1 file that will be used to retrieve image data from the label that has been given.

2.4. Application training

The CSV dataset that was created in the previous step will be separated for the training test. The next process includes label settings, configuration settings, etc. The decisive stage is in the object detection training stage.

2.5. Testing models using images

At this stage we test the software to recognize the images that we provide well, whether authentic batik or artificial batik.

2.6. Changing applications to Android apps

This step is carried out so that the application can be run on smartphone devices. Applications that was built using Windows computers need to be changed to Android apps so they can be run on smartphones. The computer training step produced models in the protobuf/.pb format. In order that the model in the format protobuf/.pb can be run on Android phones, it needs to be converted to tflite format using tfliteconverter.

3. Results

The Batik Analyzer application is designed to run using a smartphone. Smartphones can be carried everywhere because they are lighter and everyone can have them. This apps is made simple so it's easy to use. Before taking a picture, the user is asked to sign in or log in first, as shown in figure 1.a. After the user log in, the user is asked to select the method of shooting, such as 20x magnification or 60x magnification using a digital microscope, or will taking a picture with a smartphone camera. This is shown in figure 1.b.

Figure 1. (a) Display sign in user; (b) Display of picture mode selection

After shooting is complete, the application will analyze the results of fabric type predictions as shown in Figure 2. The application displays the results in the form of product types and percentage predictions.

Figure 2. Display the results of batik image analysis

4. Discussion

The results of batik magnification using 20x and 60x digital microscopes found traces that can be used to be able to distinguish the manufacturing process. The process of 'nembok' that using the hot wax is not perfect because of the limitation of the wax resist causes batik to be distinguished from artificial batik. Among them is the presence of color seepage. These are shown in Figure 3.a and 3.b.

Figure 3. (a) Magnification of imitation batik; (b) Magnification of batik

In Figure 3.a, it can be seen that at the magnification of the image using a digital microscope, the imitation of color print batik has no color permeation for the motif. Whereas in Figure 3.b there are a color permeation that occurs due to the imperfect wax blocking process. This can be used as a distinguishing feature between batik and imitation batik (artificial products). The batik analyzer application is trained to learn traits that can determine products according to their own abilities.

The application trials that have been built to analyze batik products and artificial products are shown in table 1.

Table 1. Results of trial accuracy on several types of fabrics.

Product type	Magnification 20 x	Magnification 60 x	Without magnification
Hand-written batik	64%	92%	87,5%
Stamp batik	68%	100%	70%
Color discharge printed imitation	32%	48%	80%
Cold wax printed imitation	24%	76%	60%

From the table, it can be seen that the application that built has the highest accuracy at 60x magnification. However, in the case of color discharge printed imitation, the accuracy is still low. This is possible because the color discharge printed imitation was combined with batik techniques. So the application is still confused to recognize between color discharge printed imitation and authentic batik.

5. Conclusions

Based on the results, it can be concluded that Batik Analyzer Apps using TensorFlow that has been developed is hoped to be used as an app to help distinguish authentic batik product and artificial batik product.

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